

**PROCEDURE FOR IMPLEMENTING FOREIGN
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and Problems of Developing the Economy of Uzbekistan under
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Also, the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 sets the goal of liberalizing the currency policy in Uzbekistan and implementing consistent reforms to develop the digital economy

ABSTRACT

In the conditions of the modern global economy, the procedure for carrying out foreign exchange operations is an important component of the activities of commercial banks, which directly affects not only the financial stability of banks, but also ensuring the macroeconomic balance of the country. In world practice, currency policy and the mechanisms for carrying out foreign exchange operations corresponding to it are used as the main instruments for balancing the balance of payments, ensuring the stability of the national exchange rate, and stimulating foreign economic activity.

Introduction. In the conditions of the modern global economy, the procedure for carrying out foreign exchange operations is an important component of the activities of commercial banks, which directly affects not only the financial stability of banks, but also ensuring the macroeconomic balance of the country. In world practice, currency policy and the mechanisms for carrying out foreign exchange operations corresponding to it are used as the main instruments for balancing the balance of payments, ensuring the stability of the national exchange rate, and stimulating foreign economic activity.

While the procedure for conducting foreign exchange transactions in developed countries is mainly aimed at regulating the movement of capital through discount policies, relying mainly on market mechanisms, in developing countries foreign exchange policy and administrative regulation methods are of primary importance. These differences directly affect the procedures for managing risks, ensuring liquidity, and balancing open currency positions of commercial banks in the process of conducting foreign exchange transactions.

Also, the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 sets the goal of liberalizing the currency policy in Uzbekistan and implementing consistent reforms to develop the digital economy. At the same time, the significant increase in the level of dollarization in the economy as a result of the liberalization of the currency policy, the high impact of the exchange rate on the inflation rate in the context of the transition to an inflation targeting regime, and the growth trend in the volume of external debt require the development of comprehensive measures in such areas as increasing the liquidity of the current currency market, developing the term currency market, and forming a national system for regulating cryptoassets.

Today, leading higher education and research institutions of the world, as well as reputable international financial and credit organizations, are conducting scientific research in various areas to form the practice of currency operations in commercial banks. In particular, E. Karl, S. Ray, M. Shannon expressed the opinion that “the profitability of banks in carrying out currency exchange operations is influenced by many factors, including bank-specific (internal) and macroeconomic fundamentals (external) due to state reforms and regulatory documents.” Macroeconomic factors study the behavior of the economy, and these factors are the exchange rate, interest rate, inflation rate, and gross domestic product.

T.Ovoe and A. Ovoe noted that “exchange rates affect interest rates and indirectly affect profitability through the cost of leverage.” NSSayyidi, on the other hand, stated that “high exchange rates increase the income of commercial banks from the sale of foreign currency, which increases profitability. High interest rates lead to an increase in the interest income of commercial banks, but lead to a decrease in the demand for loans and, therefore, reduce the growth of interest income.” These factors are indirect, they are not controllable, but they can significantly affect bank profitability and can be caused by the rules applied to banks. The profitability of banks from foreign exchange operations is based on speculation in the form of fees and interest arising from their operations on other sources, such as the syndrome of low buying and high selling. ATOjo and POAlege argue that “exchange rates directly affect the prices and/or profitability of tradable and non-tradable goods and how relative prices affect the allocation of resources in the short and medium term. Central banks have recently attributed the appreciation of exchange rates to the significant differences in interest rates between developed countries, which have resulted from the maintenance of near-zero interest rates in developed countries.” It is important to understand the role of foreign exchange and the exchange rate of currencies in national economies, as well as the relationship between banks as active financial institutions in foreign exchange markets, in terms of exchange rate risk.

According to ASBakare, in order to make a profit, banks, bankers and bank managers need to fully understand the concept of bank profit in foreign currency transactions and study the impact of exchange rate fluctuations on foreign exchange reserves and earnings, so that they can know what risks they can take when conducting foreign currency transactions. Thus, the constant impact of the exchange rate on the competitiveness of domestic industries in domestic and foreign markets, as well as the uncertainty arising from unexpected changes in the domestic and international macroeconomic environment, requires serious attention. Due to the economic losses caused by exchange rate instability, most countries are simultaneously reforming their exchange rates and introducing various exchange rate systems that stimulate the economies of countries or allow them to achieve a level of sustainable growth and development. For example, Pakistan changed its exchange rate system from a regulated float to a floating market system that allows commercial banks and official dealers to transact in foreign currency.

In general, currently, in the process of liberalizing the exchange rate policy in our country, attention is paid not only to improving the practice of introducing market mechanisms of exchange rate policy, but also to alternative methods of stimulating the export potential of economic entities. In particular, the practice of allocating export credits by

commercial banks to increase the competitiveness of local producers in foreign markets is one of them. Also, important steps are being taken to liberalize the trade regime, and a serious approach to ensuring sufficient conditions for our republic's membership in the World Trade Organization will also serve to increase the effectiveness of exchange rate policy mechanisms in the future.

The increasing globalization of economic relations, the deepening of the interconnection of national economies and economic integration of countries are gaining importance in the development of the world economy. In such conditions, the exchange rate is one of the main instruments for regulating the macroeconomic situation in the country, and its role in solving macroeconomic issues is increasing. In particular, the exchange rate directly affects important macroeconomic indicators, including the inflation rate, the balance of payments situation and the state budget, as well as the formation of supply and demand in the country's money market.

The type of exchange rate regime chosen is of particular importance. Today, Uzbekistan officially operates a "freely floating" exchange rate regime.

Foreign currencies in soums relatively exchange courses ¹(monthly) average)

Period	1 USA dollar (sum)	Cha nge (+/-)	1 Euro (soum)	Cha nge (+/-)	1 Russia ruble (sum)	Cha nge (+/-)
2024						
January	12,398 .38	62.4 9	13,549 .45	80.2 1	138. 87	3.18
February	12,475 .21	76.8 3	13,461 .09	- 88.36	136. 18	-2.70
March	12,550 .28	75.0 7	13,632 .88	171. 79	137. 13	0.95
April	12,670 .33	120. 05	13,616 .38	- 16.50	136. 43	-0.69
May	12,686 .96	16.6 3	13,701 .76	85.3 7	139. 44	3.00
June	12,619 .93	- 67.03	13,602 .99	- 98.77	143. 89	4.46
July	12,606 .40	- 13.53	13,670 .54	67.5 6	144. 72	0.83
August	12,634 .14	27.7 4	13,889 .41	218. 87	142. 10	-2.62
September	12,711 .30	77.1 5	14 118.32	228. 91	138. 89	-3.21

¹ Compiled by the author based on information from the site <https://cbu.uz/>

r	Octobe	12,784	73.0	13,959	-	132.	-5.94
		.37	8	.70	158.62	95	
ber	Novem	12,815	30.8	13,639	-	127.	-5.01
		.19	2	.20	320.50	94	
ber	Decem	12,874	59.7	13,483	-	125.	-2.61
		.95	6	.59	155.62	33	
2025							
	January	12,954	79.7	13,411	-	127.	1.72
		.68	3	.30	72.29	05	
ry	Februa	12,957	3.18	13,489	78.3	139.	12.7
		.86		.66	6	78	3
	March	12,920	-	13,930	441.	150.	10.8
		.74	37.12	.67	01	59	1
	April	12,944	24.1	14,508	577.	155.	4.76
		.90	6	.65	99	35	
	May	12,905	-	14,571	62.5	160.	4.84
		.04	39.86	.24	9	19	
	June	12,675	-	14,579	7.98	161.	0.86
		.17	229.87	.22		05	
	July	12,639	-	14,792	213.	160.	-0.52
		.00	36.17	.53	31	52	
	August	12,529	-	14,557	-	156.	-4.00
		.15	109.85	.62	234.91	52	
ber	Septem	12,337	-	14,470	-	148.	-7.53
		.60	191.55	.97	86.65	99	

1 above show that significant fluctuations were observed in the monthly average exchange rates of foreign currencies against the soum during 2024–2025 . In particular, the overall dynamics of the US dollar exchange rate was characterized by relatively moderate changes, and the soum's tendency to gradually depreciate against the dollar during this period remained. This is explained by the increase in the volume of foreign trade operations, demand for imported goods, and the population's expectations regarding the currency.

The dynamics of the euro exchange rate are characterized by a high level of volatility. In particular, sharp changes in the euro exchange rate in the second half of 2024 and the first quarter of 2025 indicate that it was formed under the influence of instability in international financial markets, decisions of the European Central Bank on interest rates, and global inflationary processes. This situation requires strengthening risk management mechanisms in commercial banks when conducting currency transactions related to the euro.

Changes in the exchange rate of the Russian ruble against the soum are mainly determined by foreign political and geopolitical factors, as well as structural changes taking place in the Russian economy. Fluctuations in the ruble have a significant impact on the conversion operations and short-term currency positions of commercial banks in the context of extensive regional trade relations.

In general, the dynamics of exchange rates reflected in the table clearly demonstrates the need to improve the procedure for conducting currency transactions in commercial banks. In particular, in conditions of volatility in exchange rates, the active use of spot, forward and swap transactions by banks, strict control of open currency positions and strengthening of mechanisms for hedging currency risks are of great importance. At the same time, these exchange rate fluctuations are considered a factor increasing the impact of the Central Bank's monetary policy and interventions in the foreign exchange market on the activities of commercial banks.

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